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Research Study

The Aetiological Profile Of Seizure In Patients Admitted In Teaching Hospital Of East India

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Seizure is common disease worldwide. It affects all the age groups and both the genders. There are several types as per International league against epilepsy (ILAE-2017). It can be broadly a focal onset, generalized onset or unknown onset seizure. Aetiologically it can be due to infection, metabolic abnormality, head trauma, cerebrovascular events, and alcohol and unknown reasons. **Aim:** This study attempts to find out the aetiological profile and helps in knowing the reversible and preventable causes of seizure in patients admitted in hospital. **Methods:** This is a retrospective analytical study on patients admitted in hospital. We went through the case records for history and investigations. Seizure was classified clinically based on records. **Results:** In our study, the total number of seizure cases were 127, where males (n=78) were more than females (n=49). Out of all the cases maximum affected patients were in the age group 50-69 years (29%, n=37) followed by 13-29 years (25%, n=32), 70-89 years (22.04%, n=28), and 30-49 years (13.38%, n=17) while least number of cases were above 90 years (10.23%, n=13). Generalized onset seizure was seen more frequently (68.50%, n=87) than focal onset (31.50%, n=40). We found cerebrovascular accident (CVA) (25.19%, n=32), metabolic derangements (16.53%, n=21), idiopathic (14.17%, n=18), central nervous system (CNS) infection (11.02%, n=14) as the commoner reasons behind seizures while brain tumour (7.87%, n=10), encephalomalacia with gliosis and parenchymal calcification (5.51%, n=7 each), alcohol withdrawal (4.72%, n=6), focal brain oedema (3.93%, n=5), poisoning and ring enhancing lesions (3.14%, n=4 each) were the less commoner ones. **Conclusion:** Generalized type seizure was noted more than focal onset type. Most frequently affected age groups were in 50-69 years and 13-29 years groups. Commoner aetiology of seizures noticed were cerebrovascular accident (CVA) (25.19%, n=32), metabolic derangements (16.53%, n=21), idiopathic (14.17%, n=18).

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INTRODUCTION:

Seizure means the action of capturing someone or something using force. The official definition of a seizure is "a transient occurrence of signs and/or symptoms due to an abnormal excessive or synchronous neuronal activity in the brain." It can be life-threatening especially if it is generalized type. The reported prevalence of depression in people living with epilepsy varies between 12% and 37% in community settings (1, 2). The prevalence of suicidal ideation and attempt among people with epilepsy were 29.8% and 14.1%, respectively (3).

There are many types of seizure and so are the risk factors and the aetiological profile. It is not an uncommon disease worldwide but in developing countries, it has been estimated that incidence rate for epilepsy was higher (about 100-190/100,000/year) than those in developed countries (40-70/100,000/year) (4).

In developed countries, aetiology of epilepsy is also age-dependent. In children, about 20% are remote symptomatic, 50% are cryptogenic while 30% are idiopathic. However, in elderly, about 55% is remote symptomatic while 45% are idiopathic/cryptogenic (5). There is considerable variability in causes and risk factors for seizures and epilepsy in the elderly (6). The most frequently reported risk factor was cerebrovascular disease (30-70%). Tumours, usually metastatic or aggressive gliomas, were less frequent (10-15%). Metabolic disorders (e.g. uraemia, hepatic failure, non-ketotic hyperglycaemia, hypoglycaemia, hyponatremia, hypocalcaemia, etc), toxic causes (e.g. drugs and alcohol), and cerebral hypoxia secondary to various causes of syncope accounted for 10% of all other seizures, especially for the acute symptomatic type.

AIMS: The aim of the study was to find out the aetiological profile of seizure in patients admitted in a teaching hospital of east India.

Material: We have selected total 127 cases for whom proper clinical records was available and CT brain and EEG was done. Additional investigations like MRI brain, MRV and cerebrospinal fluid analysis if done were also included in selected cases. Data was analysed using Microsoft excel 2007 software.

Methods: This was a retrospective analytical study. We went through the case records for history and investigations. Seizure was classified as per International League against Epilepsy (ILAE)-2017 basic version.

ILAE 2017 Classification of seizure types-basic version-

Focal onset- (a) Aware / Impaired awareness

- (b) Motor onset/ Nonmotor onset

-(c) Focal to bilateral tonic clonic

Generalized onset - (a) Motor-Tonic clonic/other motor

- (b) Nonmotor(absence)

Unknown onset -(a) Motor-Tonic clonic /other motor

- (b) Nonmotor

-(c) Unclassified

Duration- 1st April 2017 to 30th April 2018.

Inclusion criteria:

Patients of age 13 years and above with seizure.

Exclusion criteria:

1-Insufficient clinical data

2-Definite syncope

3-Movement disorder

4-pseudoseizures

5-Hyperventilation syndrome

RESULTS-

In our study, as seen in figure: 1, the total number of seizure cases were 127, where males (61%, n=78) exceeded females (39%, n=49). Figure: 2 shows that maximum affected patients were in the age group 50-69 years (29%, n=37) followed by 13-29 years (25%, n=32), 70-89 years (22.04%, n=28), and 30-49 years (13.38%, n=17) while least number of cases were above 90 years (10.23%, n=13). Almost in all the age groups males were more affected than females. Generalized onset seizure was seen in more patients (68.50%, n=87) than focal onset (31.50%, n=40). As per Figure: 3, in the generalized onset category males (65.52%, n=57) were more than females (34.48%, n=30) while it was reverse in focal onset category where females (67.50%, n=27) were more affected than males (32.50%, n=13). Out of total focal onset seizures, 19 had no cognitive impairment, 13 were having cognitive impairment while 8 had secondary

generalization (table: 1). Aetiologically total number of cases was 136 wherein 9 cases had two possible

causes of seizure combined and metabolic derangement was the second one.

Figure: 1-Gender distribution

Figure: 2-Age group distribution

Figure: 3-Gender wise seizure prevalence

Table: 1-Gender predilection of type of focal seizure

Type of focal seizure	Male		Female	
	%	n	%	n
Without cognitive impairment	15	6	32.50	13
With cognitive impairment	10	4	22.50	9
Secondary generalization	7.50	3	12.50	5

Table:2-Distribution of aetiological factors

Aetiological factor	Percentage	Number	Male	Female
Stroke	25.19	32	20	12
Metabolic derangements	15.53	21	12	9
idiopathic	14.17	18	10	8
CNS infection	11.02	14	8	6
Brain tumour	7.87	10	5	5
Encephalomalcia /gliosis	5.51	7	4	3
Parenchymal calcification	5.51	7	4	3
Alcohol withdrawal	4.72	6	6	0
Focal brain oedema	3.93	5	3	2
Poisoning	3.14	4	2	2
Ring enhancing lesions	3.14	4	3	1
Cortical vein thrombosis	1.57	2	0	2
Multiple punctate haemorrhages	1.57	2	2	0
Mesial temporal lobe atrophy	1.57	2	1	1
Eclampsia	1.57	2	0	2

Table:3-Aetiological factors and type of seizure

Aetiology	Generalized seizure	Focal seizure
Stroke	17.32%(22)	7.87%(10)
Metabolic	14.17%(18)	2.36%(3)
Brain tumours	2.36%(3)	5.51%(7)
Idiopathic	10.23%(13)	3.93%(5)
CNS infection	7.08%(9)	3.93%(5)
Encephalomalacia/gliosis	1.57%(2)	3.93%(5)

Table:4-Aetiological distribution in different age groups

Common aetiology	Age group (age in years)				
	13-29	30-49	50-69	70-89	Above 90
Idiopathic	37.50%(12)	11.76%(2)	8.10%(3)	3.57%(1)	-
CNS infection	28.14%(9)	17.64%(3)	8.10%(3)	14.28%(4)	15.38%(2)
Poisoning	9.38%(3)	-	-	-	-
Brain tumours	6.25%(2)	-	-	-	15.38%(2)

Metabolic derangements	-	35.29%(6)	13.51%(5)	17.85%(5)	30.76%%(4)
Stroke	-	11.76%(2)	40.54%(15)	35.71%(10)	23.07%(3)

Aetiological profile of seizure in stroke:

Out of all 32 cases of stroke, infarct was seen more (59.37%, n=19) than bleed (40.62%, n=13) as a factor

behind seizure. Amongst stroke due to infarct 76% had focal seizure while bleed was seen in 59% cases with generalised seizure.

Table:5-Metabolic profile of seizure

Associated conditions	Hyponatremia	Hypoglycaemia	Uremic encephalopathy	Hepatic encephalopathy
CVA	9.52% (2)	9.52% (2)	4.76% (1)	0
CNS Infection	9.52% (2)	0	0	0
Tumour	0	0	0	0
Alcohol	0	9.52% (2)	0	4.76% (1)
Gliosis	4.76% (1)	0	4.76% (1)	0
Others (Normal CT Brain without alcohol abuse and poisoning)	19.04% (4)	4.76% (1)	4.76% (1)	14.28% (3)

Distribution of seizure in CNS infection:

Most common cause of seizure in central nervous system infection was viral meningoencephalitis (42.9%, n=6), followed by tuberculous meningoencephalitis (28.6%, n=4), neurocysticercosis and cerebral malaria (14.3%, n=2 in each). Of these, all the viral meningoencephalitis, cerebral malaria and 50% of tuberculous meningoencephalitis patients had

generalized seizure while it was focal onset in cases of neurocysticercosis.

Abnormal EEG: Electroencephalogram showed abnormal records only in 33.8 % (n= 43) cases. Out of these, 69.77 % (n=30) had generalized seizures while 30.23 % (n=13) had focal seizures.

Table:6-CT head findings in seizure patients

CT Brain findings	Percent cases(number)
Infarct	11.02% (14)
Meningoencephalitis	8.66% (11)
Parenchymal bleed	7% (9)
Tumours	5.5% (7)
Calcifications	5.5% (7)
Encephalomalacia/gliosis	5.5% (7)
Ring enhancing lesions	3.14% (4)
Subarachnoid haemorrhage	2.36% (3)
Brain abscess	1.57% (2)
Subdural haematoma	0.78% (1)
Generalized atrophy	7.08% (9)
Normal without atrophy	36.22% (46)

Table:7-MRI brain findings in seizure patients

MRI brain findings	Percent cases(number)
Infarct	9.8% (5)
Meningoencephalitis	9.8% (5)
Focal brain oedema	9.8% (5)
Tumours	5.8% (3)
Tuberculoma	3.9% (2)
Multiple punctate haemorrhages	3.9% (2)
Mesial temporal atrophy	3.9% (2)
Generalized atrophy	17.64% (9)
Normal without atrophy	35.29% (18)

DISCUSSION:

Our study reveals a male predominance which was almost like results noted by Sheikh NA et al (7) (57.6% males and 42.4% females) and Prakash B et al(8) (55% and 45%). Seeing at the maximum age group affected in our study, there was no similarity as we found most of the cases in 50 to 69 years in contrast to above two quoted studies where it was in 25 to 35 years. In the present study generalized onset seizure was seen commoner than focal onset type and it was near to the values as seen by Narayanan JT et al (9) and Sheikh NA et al (7), who found 55% and 53.5% generalized type seizure respectively. However, there was a contrast finding in another study (10) where focal onset seizure was predominant type.

We observed cerebrovascular accident, metabolic derangements, idiopathic and central nervous system infection (in decreasing order) as the commoner causes behind seizure. Stroke was the commonest while idiopathic, CNS infection and metabolic derangements (in decreasing order) were the commoner aetiologies as found in a study by Sarabjot Kaur et al(11). There was no gender predilection of aetiological factors in seizure except for alcohol withdrawal and eclampsia. It was seen in a different study that CNS infection and metabolic derangements (32% each) and stroke (21%) were the common causes of seizure (9) while another one (12) was showed aetiological profile like stroke (21%), idiopathic (19%), CNS infection (17%) and metabolic derangements (15%).

Aetiological profile for generalized seizure in our study was not exactly same but comparable to results obtained by Hirani and Shrivastava et al (13) while, Quraishi et al (14), reported that the most common aetiologies of generalized seizures in adults were CNS infections and

stroke (29.7% each), followed by idiopathic (27%), metabolic (10.8%), and tumours (2.7%).

Amongst causes of focal seizures was stroke, brain tumours, encephalomalacia with gliosis, CNS infection and idiopathic were the common factors while Sendil et al(15) noted stroke as the most common aetiology (38.8% cases); other causes were idiopathic (33.3%), brain tumours (22.2%), and CNS infections (5.5%). Similar results were seen in other studies (11, 13, 16). However, Chalasani and Kumar (10), observed that the most common aetiology of adult onset focal seizures was CNS infections (52.7%), followed by stroke (27.3%), idiopathic (10.9%), brain tumours (5.4%), and trauma (3.6%).

Age distribution of causes of seizure in our study revealed idiopathic (37.50%) and CNS infection (28.14%) as the common aetiological factors in patients less than 30 years of age while patients above 50 years had stroke (35.90%) and metabolic derangements (17.94%) as the two most common causes behind seizure. Patients in age group 30 to 49 years had seizures caused mainly by metabolic derangements (35.29%), followed by CNS infection (17.64%). S.Kaur et al (11), found idiopathic (44.4%) as the most common aetiology in seizure below 20 years. While above 20 years but below 40 years it was noted that CNS infection (66.7%) was the most common factor. In a cross-sectional study by Ashwin et al (12), stroke and metabolic derangements were the main causes in 50-59 years' age group.

In our case infarct ((59.37%) was more contributing to seizure than bleeds (40.62%) supported by Sendil et al (14), Quraishi et al (15), and Amravathi et al(16). Focal seizure was more common in infarct while bleed was responsible for generalized type as also noted in other studies (14, 15, and 16).

Metabolic abnormality (most commonly hyponatremia) was noted in many cases (16.53%), It was the third common cause of seizure in this study. Here 42.9% metabolic derangements were associated with some other aetiological factors while 57.14% were without such association. So far as we know, almost all the other studies have not mentioned of the associated condition with metabolic derangements. We found alcohol withdrawal(4.72%) less frequently compared to other metabolic derangements(16.53%).Kanitkar et al(17) found alcohol withdrawal(31%) to be most common metabolic abnormality in their study while Sarabjot Kaur et al(11), found equal contribution by alcohol withdrawal and hyponatremia(each 25%).In another study metabolic derangement (6%) and electrolyte imbalance (8%) were quoted separately(21) .

Considering the infections, we noted viral meningoencephalitis (42.9%, n=6), followed by tuberculous meningoencephalitis (28.6%, n=4) to be the common CNS infections causing seizure where all the viral meningoencephalitis cases and 50% of tuberculous meningoencephalitis cases had generalized type of seizure. All the neurocysticercosis patients had focal onset type seizure. In a study (11), the common infections were CNS TB (42.8%), followed by neurocysticercosis (28.5%) and viral meningoencephalitis (14.3%) while Kanitkar *et al* (17), noted CNS TB in 60% and neurocysticercosis in 40% cases.

Abnormality in EEG was noted only in 33.8% cases. Out of these, 69.77% had generalized seizures while 30.23 % had focal seizures. This abnormal record was lower compared to results (45%) seen by Swati Sunil Jagtap et al (18) and 52.78% by Nawaz A. Sheikh et al (19). We found abnormal EEG in 67.44% males and 30.23% females which is supported by another study (19), with similar results.

We found normal CT head in 36.22% with predominant lesions being infarct (11.02%), meningoencephalitis (8.66%) and parenchymal bleed (7%).Hirani and Shrivastava (13) have noted normal CT head in 40% patients; most common CT finding was infarct (16%), followed by ring enhancing lesions (12%), tuberculoma (12%), brain tumour (8%), intracranial haemorrhage (8%), and brain abscess (2%).

On assessing MRI findings, out of all cases MRI brain was done in 40.15% cases. We found infarct, meningoencephalitis and focal brain oedema equally

(9.80% in each) followed by tumour (5.8%).There was no abnormality in 37.25% cases. Sarabjot Kaur et al (11), found it normal in 30% patients. The most common MRI abnormal findings were infarct (16.3%), followed by gliosis and tumour (8.3% each); tuberculoma, neurocysticercosis, and encephalitis/meningitis (6.9% each). Pannag KN et al (20), reported that MRI brain was normal in 46% and the most common pathological findings on MRI were postischemia/haemorrhagic changes (20%), followed by tuberculoma (9.7%), tumour (9%), mesial temporal sclerosis (3%), neurocysticercosis (2.4%), encephalitis (2.4%), vascular malformation (1%), and progressive multifocal leukoencephalopathy (0.6%).

CONCLUSION:

We observed that there were more males than females and age group (50-69 years and 13-29 years) were more commonly affected by seizure. Commonest aetiology of seizure was stroke which was followed by metabolic derangements and idiopathic conditions. There were considerable number of cases where the aetiological factors of seizure could be prevented or avoided. Out of all the case CT head was normal in 36.22% while MRI brain in those where done was normal in 35.29%. An EEG does not need to be abnormal always in seizure patients.

LIMITATIONS: A larger population based prospective study may provide clearer results.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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